

Studies on the Chelation of 3-Hydroxynaphthalene-2-Carboxylic Acid with Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) in Dioxane Medium

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Potentiometric studies have been carried on complexes of 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid with Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) in 50 vol % dioxane-water medium at these temperatures and ionic strength 0.1 M (KNO₃). Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as used by Irving and Rossotti has been applied to determine stability constants of the complexes. The log K values have been computed by various computational methods. Free energy, enthalpy and entropy changes have also been evaluated. The thermodynamic stability constants have also been reported by determining the stability constants of the complexes at 30° and four different ionic strengths.

THE capacity of 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid to act as an efficient complexing agent for different metal ions has been studied by various workers under different experimental conditions^{1,2}. The stoichiometric stability constants, thermodynamic functions and thermodynamic stability constants of few lanthanons, Zn(II), Cd(II) and UO₂(II) complexes with the above ligand in aqueous-dioxane (50% v/v) at three temperatures and four ionic strengths have already been reported in our earlier communications³.

In the present study, the stoichiometric stability constants, thermodynamic functions of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) with 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid have been determined in aqueous-dioxane (50% v/v) at 20°, 30° and 40° at 0.1M(KNO₃) ionic strength following Irving-Rossotti titration technique⁴. Thermodynamic stability constants have also been reported by determining the stability constants of the complexes at 30° and four ionic strengths of 0.05M, 0.10M, 0.15M and 0.20M(KNO₃) and then extrapolating to zero ionic strength.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The double distilled CO₂ free water was used in all experimental works. Dioxane was purified by the recommended procedure⁵. Metal nitrate solutions were prepared by dissolving the corresponding metal salts in double distilled water. The concentration of metal ions were determined volumetrically with E. D. T. A⁶, and the standard solutions (0.01M) were prepared after proper dilution of the stock solutions. In case of copper nitrate fairly concentrated stock solution was made and was diluted immediately before use. This was done to avoid formation of any hydrolytic product because of the rather low pH of hydrolysis of Cu(II)⁷. The ligand solution (0.05M) was prepared in dioxane.

The mole ratio of metal to ligand was kept 1:5 in order to fulfil the maximum coordination number of the metal ion.

Photovolt digital pH meter type M-120(U.S.A.) with glass and calomel electrode assembly, calibrated by suitable buffers before use and having an accuracy of ±0.002 units was used to measure pH during titrations which were carried out in a cell immersed in a thermostated bath maintained at (20±0.1)°, (30±0.1)° and (40±0.1)°.

The three solutions (total volume 50 ml in each case) were prepared as follows—

A, 1.0×10⁻²M HNO₃, B, 1.0×10⁻²M HNO₃+5.0×10⁻²M ligand, C, 1.0×10⁻²M HNO₃+5.0×10⁻²M ligand+1.0×10⁻²M metal ion solution, such that the concentrations of the common ingredients were identical in different cases. An appropriate quantity of potassium nitrate solution (1.0M) was added to maintain the desired ionic strength. The above solutions were titrated against potassium hydroxide (0.1M) solution prepared in aqueous-dioxane (50%, v/v) and standardised against standard potassium hydrogen-phthalate solution.

Results and Discussion

The difference in the amount of potassium hydroxide used for the last two titrations (B and C) is a measure of extent of complexation. From the titration curves it is observed that the metal ligand curve is well separated from the ligand titration curve proving that the liberation of protons is due to chelation.

Values of formation functions \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL were calculated using the standard expressions⁴.

* M = mol ohm-3

TABLE 1—VALUES OF PROTONATION CONSTANTS, STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS AT THREE TEMPERATURES AND $\mu=0.10M$

Cation	Constants	Method	Temperature			ΔG (Kcal mole ⁻¹)			ΔH (Kcal mole ⁻¹) at 30°C	ΔS (calmole ⁻¹) degree ⁻¹) at 30°C	
			20°C	30°C	40°C	20°C	30°C	40°C			
H(I)	$\log P_{K_1^H}$		11.52	11.25	10.95						
	$\log P_{K_2^H}$		2.78	2.65	2.45						
	$\log P_{\beta_2^H}$		14.30	13.90	13.40						
Cu(II)	$\log K_1$	(i)	9.38	9.30	9.30						
		(ii)	9.38	9.30	9.30						
		(iii)	9.43	9.36	9.33						
		(iv)	9.38	9.29	9.29						
	$\log K_2$	(i)	6.50	7.18	7.20						
		(ii)	6.50	7.18	7.20						
		(iii)	6.47	7.06	7.15						
		(iv)	6.50	7.19	7.21						
	$\log \beta_2^2$		15.88	16.48	16.50	21.29	22.84	23.63	+13.2	119	
	Co(II)	$\log K_1$	(i)	7.70	7.45	7.39					
			(ii)	7.70	7.45	7.39					
			(iii)	7.79	7.44	7.37					
(iv)			7.41	7.05	7.01						
$\log K_2$		(i)	7.22	7.16	7.06						
		(ii)	7.22	7.16	7.06						
		(iii)	7.20	7.13	7.04						
		(iv)	7.52	7.56	7.44						
$\log \beta_2$		14.93	14.61	14.45	20.02	20.25	20.69	-10.3	32.8		
Ni(II)	$\log K_1$	(i)	7.20	6.81	6.80						
		(ii)	7.20	6.81	6.80						
		(iii)	7.24	6.82	6.71						
		(iv)	7.01	6.47	6.52						
	$\log K_2$	(i)	6.45	6.41	6.29						
		(ii)	6.45	6.41	6.29						
		(iii)	6.34	6.36	6.20						
		(iv)	6.64	6.75	6.57						
	$\log \beta_2$		13.65	13.22	13.09	18.30	18.32	18.74	-12.8	18.1	

- (i) Bjerrum's half integral method ;
(ii) Graphical method ;
(iii) Interpolation at \bar{n} various values ;
(iv) Method of successive approximations.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF THE PROTONATIONS CONSTANTS OF THE LIGAND AND CONCENTRATION STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES AT 30°C.

Cation	Constants	Method	$\mu=0.05$	$\mu=0.10$	$\mu=0.15$	$\mu=0.20M$	
H(I)	$\log P_{K_1^H}$		11.30	11.25	11.20	11.15	
	$\log P_{K_2^H}$		2.70	2.65	2.60	2.55	
	$\log P_{\beta_2^H}$		14.00	13.90	13.80	13.70	
Cu(II)	$\log K_1$	(i)	9.45	9.30	9.22	9.05	
		(ii)	9.45	9.30	9.22	9.05	
		(iii)	9.47	9.36	9.32	9.04	
		(iv)	9.44	9.29	9.21	9.04	
	$\log K_2$	(i)	7.48	7.18	7.02	6.89	
		(ii)	7.48	7.18	—	6.89	
		(iii)	7.46	7.06	—	6.85	
		(iv)	7.49	7.19	7.03	6.90	
	$\log \beta_1$		16.93	16.48	16.24	15.94	
	Co(II)	$\log K_1^I$	(i)	7.73	7.45	7.25	7.15
			(ii)	—	7.45	7.25	7.15
			(iii)	—	7.44	7.32	7.18
(iv)			7.33	7.05	6.94	6.84	
$\log K_2$		(i)	7.45	7.16	6.79	6.70	
		(ii)	7.45	7.16	—	6.70	
		(iii)	7.34	7.13	—	6.70	
		(iv)	7.86	7.56	7.10	7.02	
$\log \beta_2$			15.19	14.61	14.04	13.86	
Ni(II)		$\log K_1$	(i)	7.04	6.81	6.58	6.42
			(ii)	7.04	6.81	6.58	6.42
			(iii)	7.03	6.82	6.56	6.44
	(iv)		6.77	6.47	6.13	5.97	
	$\log K_2$	(i)	6.50	6.41	6.36	6.20	
		(ii)	6.50	6.41	—	6.20	
		(iii)	6.39	6.36	—	6.13	
		(iv)	6.77	6.75	6.81	6.65	
	$\log \beta_2$		13.54	13.33	12.94	12.62	

- (i) Bijerrum's half integral method ;
- (ii) Graphical method;
- (iii) Interpolation of various \bar{n} values ;
- (iv) Method of successive approximations.

The calculations of conditional stability constants of proton complexes were done by plotting \bar{n}_A versus pH and then applying various computational methods^{8,9}. The mean values of protonation constants of the ligand at three temperatures, 0.1M ionic strength and four ionic strengths, at 30° have been summarized in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively.

The stoichiometric metal-ligand stability constants have been obtained by analysis of formation curves obtained by plotting \bar{n} versus pL . These plots indicate that the values of \bar{n} obtained are of the order of two for all the metal ions under study indicating the formation of both 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. Bjerrum's half integral method⁸, interpolation at various \bar{n} values, graphical method⁹ and extended to dioxane-water mixture by Van Uitert and Haas¹⁰ were used to calculate log K values.

Since the ratio of successive constants was less than 10^4 , the method of successive approximations was used to refine the values of stability constants obtained by half-integral method. However, in case of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes at 30° and 0.15M ionic strength, since there are very few values of \bar{n} above one, pL at $1.5\bar{n}$ could not be found out and the value of log K_2 was obtained by interpolation at mid-point using the following relationship

$$\log K_1 K_2 = 2pL \text{ (at } \bar{n}=1\text{)}$$

In case of Co(II) complex at 30° and 0.05M ionic strength since there are very few values of the \bar{n} below one, pL at $0.5\bar{n}$ could not be found out and so the value of log K_1 was obtained by interpolation at midpoint using the above relationship. Since the method of interpolation at various \bar{n} values and graphical method was inapplicable in the above cases, the log K values thus obtained, however, have been refined by the method of successive approximations⁹. The value of stepwise stability constants obtained by various methods and of overall stability constants obtained by the method of successive approximations have been reported (Tables 1 and 2).

The small difference between successive constants suggests that the formation of two types of complexes ML_1 and ML_2 proceed simultaneously and may be attributed to the smaller steric hindrance offered by 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid as compared with coordinated water molecule.

The order of overall stability is Cu(II) > Co(II) > Ni(II) which is not in accordance with Irving-Williams order¹¹. The greater stability of Co(II) than Ni(II) complex may be attributed to the additional stabilization due to Jahn-Teller distortion present in case of Co(II). The stability of the Cu(II) complex is much higher than can be expected from its ionic radius or electronegativity. This extra stability of the Cu(II) complex, being square planar, has been attributed to Jahn-Teller stabilization.

The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) accompanying complexation have been determined using the temperature coefficient and gibbs-Helmholtz equation, using the refined log K values (Table 1). The free energies of formation (ΔG) of the complexes have more negative values with increase of temperature showing that complex formation is a spontaneous process. The enthalpy change (ΔH) is positive for the Cu(II) complex showing that the reaction is endothermic, whereas ΔH is negative for Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes, which is favourable for the formation of these complexes. The entropy change (ΔS) is positive in all cases and favours the formation of complexes. The greater value of entropy for Cu(II) complex justified that the entropy change (ΔS) favours its formation through the enthalpy change (ΔH) does not favour complex formation.

The metal-ligand stability data at various μ values (Table 2) reveal that log β_2 values decrease with an increase in the ionic strength of the medium. According to Hückel¹³, the activity of the metal ion for its interaction with other molecular species varies in inverse proportion to the ionic strength of the medium. On this basis, the decrease in stability for 3-hydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid complexes with the metal ions under study in solution of increasing ionic strength is justified.

The values of log step stability constants at various ionic strengths extrapolated to zero ionic strength gave step thermodynamic stability constant¹⁴. These values are shown in Table 3 as log $K_1^{\mu=0}$ and log $K_2^{\mu=0}$. Their sum is shown as calculated log $K^{\mu=0}$. The values of overall stability constant log β_2 at various ionic strengths were likewise extrapolated to zero ionic strength and the overall thermodynamic stability constants thus obtained have been symbolised as experimental log $K^{\mu=0}$.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC CONSTANTS AND FREE ENERGIES AT 30°C.

	Metal ions		
	Cu(II)	Co(II)	Ni(II)
log $K_1^{\mu=0}$	9.58	7.49	7.03
log $K_2^{\mu=0}$	7.68	8.14	8.82
Calcd log $K^{\mu=0}$	17.26	15.63	13.15
Exptl log $K^{\mu=0}$	17.26	15.63	13.85
ΔF_1 (Kcal mole ⁻¹)	-13.28	-10.38	-9.74
ΔF_2 (Kcal mole ⁻¹)	-10.64	-11.28	-9.45
Calcd ΔF (Kcal mole ⁻¹)	-23.92	-21.66	-19.19
Exptl ΔF (Kcal mole ⁻¹)	-23.92	-21.66	-19.19

Ligational standard free energy change was obtained from the expression

$$\Delta F = -2.303 RT \log K^{\circ}$$

The values of $\log K$, ΔG , ΔH and ΔS are reported in required number of significant figures¹⁵. The error limits are ± 0.05 for $\log K$ values. The precision of ΔG or ΔF , ΔH and ΔS values are ± 0.08 Kcal mole⁻¹, ± 0.1 Kcal mole⁻¹ and 0.2 cal degree⁻¹ mole⁻¹ respectively for the results reported in this paper¹⁶.

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